

Sample Name: PET Virgin 1 µm
Material: Polyethylene terephthalate
Size: <1 µm
Production Partner: TNO
Storage Conditions: Refrigerated

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 2,53 µm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $3,6 \times 10^{11}$ particles per gram
- 19949 cm²/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% C₁₀H₈O₄ (PET) determined by XRF
- No changes due to milling observed in FTIR spectrum
- Not able to obtain a cathodoluminescence spectrum

Description of terms

- D[4,3]: Volume mean (µm)
- D[3,2]: Surface area mean (µm)
- D[2,1]: Spherical particle mean (µm)
- D[1,0]: Number length mean (µm)
- D_{50_v}: Median diameter (volume basis, µm)
- D_{50_N}: Median diameter (number basis, µm)
- N_w: Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w: Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm²/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
3,25	2,18	1,52	1,15	0,89	2,53	$3,6 \times 10^{11}$	19949

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₄	99,937
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	210
Cl	225
Ti	5
Cr	21
Mn	1
Fe	80
Ni	22
Cu	3
Zn	8
Zr	1
Pb	20

Chemical Bonding (Using μ-FTIR provided by TNO)Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

Not available